

Greek Politics and the Migratory Influx of 2015

“If you don’t expect the unexpected you will never find (truth)”

Heraclitus

“The goddess History may be in possession of the truth, the whole truth and nothing but the truth -but to the historian she will at best- vouchsafe a glimpse. Never will she surrender the hole of her treasure”

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¹Pieter Geyl, *Use and Abuse of History* (New Haven, Yale University Press, 1955, reprint Archon Books, 1970) pp 62-64) in Trachtenberg (2009), p.23

Abstract

In 2015 a disproportionate migratory influx caused soaked waves to Europe. Generators of this influx were considered to be primarily the Syrian war and secondly the instrumentalization of the migratory flow by the Turkish government. This dissertation aims at inquiring whether a third factor can be added, contributing to a better understanding of the case that being Greece's political stand during the first quarter of 2015.

The theoretical part will demonstrate how the distinctiveness of the refugee may be used by nation states to transform migrants into weapons and under which conditions this is considered as Coercive Engineered Migration practice. The research will be carried out using Critical Discourse Analysis in the form of Discourse Critical Analysis as the data represent ongoing discourses between states and institutions.

The dissertation's findings lean on the conclusion that Greece did deploy a rhetoric that could exemplify the practice of CEM. At the same time the preferred migratory path shifted from that of Libya-Italy in 2014 to Turkey Greece in 2015. Whereas, a causal link between Greece's actions and the migratory inflation was not firmly proven, the simultaneous developments of the investigated events establish a strong connection between them. According to the conclusions reached in this thesis, the claim that CEM was exerted by Greece (in an implicit and indirect manner and method) has a valid case.

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CONTENTS LIST

1. INTRODUCTION	6
2.1. HYPOTHESIS AND RESEARCH QUESTION	7
2.2. DELIMITATIONS	7
2.3. THESIS STRUCTURE	8
3. MAPPING THE FIELD IN EUROPE	9
3.1. THE CHANGE OF FLOWS FROM 2014 TO 2015	11
4. THEORETICAL STRUCTURE	13
4.1. THE DISTINCTIVENESS OF ASYLUM SEEKERS AND REFUGEES	13
4.2. ASYLUM SEEKER-REFUGEES AND NATION STATES	15
4.3. REFUGEES IN THE SPECTRUM OF GLOBAL POLITICS	19
4.4. COERCIVE ENGINEERED MIGRATION	20
4.4.1. DEFINITION	20
4.4.2. ACTORS	21
4.4.3. MECHANISMS	22
4.4.4. VULNERABILITY OF LIBERAL STATES	24
5. TURKEY, GREECE, REFUGEES AND CEM	25
5.1. TURKEY	25
5.2. GREECE	26
6. METHODOLOGY	29
6.1. DATA SELECTION AND COLLECTION	31
6.1.1. TESTIMONIAL BOOK	32
6.1.2. TEXTS	32
6.2. DATA PRESENTATION-ELABORATION	32
7. DATA ANALYSIS	33
7.1. VAROUFAKIS' BOOK	34
7.1.1. DISCOURSE HISTORICAL ANALYSIS	36
7.2. ALEXIS TSIPRAS- THE GREEK PRIME MINISTER	37
7.2.1. DISCOURSE HISTORICAL ANALYSIS	39
7.3. CROSSING NARRATIVES- DISCUSSION	40

8. NARRATIVES AND CEM	<u>41</u>
9. CONCLUSIONS	<u>44</u>
10. FINAL REMARKS	<u>45</u>

Abbreviations

BBC- British Broadcasting Corporation

CEAS- Common European Asylum System

CEM- Coersive Engineered Migration

EU- European Union

EURODAC- European Asylum Dactylosvopy Database

FRONTEX- Frontieres Exterieures (External Frontiers) The European Border and Coast Guard Agency

IOM- International Organisation of Migration

ISIS- Islamic State of Iraq and Al-Sham

NGO- Non Governmental Organization

UNHCR- The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

1. Introduction

The root cause that led to this essay emerged from the simple question: “Why 170.100 migrants entered Italy in 2014 and 153.842 in 2015, whereas 43.500 entered Greece in 2014 and 857.363 in 2015 (IOM)? Namely, why the entries in Italy were reduced whereas in Greece were skyrocketing?”

For me as a researcher, the challenge was to ascertain “Could something else than war to be the cause?”.

2015 will be marked in history as the year of an unprecedented arrival of immigrants in Europe. In less than a year, in a sudden inflation of the regular migratory flow 1.046.599 people entered Europe, 857.363 of them crossing the borders from Turkey to Greece creating a state of humanitarian emergency on European soil. The majority originated from war-enmeshed Syria and most of the rest were also coming from conflict involved areas, such as Afghanistan.

The main cause of the constant, after the breakout of the Syrian war in 2011, migratory flow had always been war and conflicts in home countries. The great inflation of 2015 however was not compatible with the intensity of war developments in Syria (the main country of migrants’ origin) nor could explain the sudden change of the preferable migratory path to Europe which until 2014 was the path from Libya to Italy. So, after 2016 a new cause emerged in the public and scientific discourse that attributed to Turkey the role of manipulator of the refugee flows towards Europe promoting this way specific demands to EU (Greenhill, Gocalp Aras).

It is curious though that the State and actions of Greece during 2015 were never put under scrutiny to a possible relation to the influx. Throughout the surge period of 2015, Greece was in a terrible predicament due to the ongoing economic crisis and a subsequent political “earthquake” in January of 2015. Any attempt to decipher the perplexed realities concerning these migration episodes without considering Greece, where the episodes took place, could be compared with an attempt to diagnose and treat a patient suffering from two serious diseases fully ignoring one of them and yet wondering, why the patient’s condition is not improving.

2015 was a unique year for Greece as after almost 8 years of regression a left government took for the first time in history the wheel of power. The new government had a distinct ideology

starkly depicted in its rhetoric. In my estimation the new political wind that blew in Greece reached places far outside the Greek borders.

Therefore, this study attempts to disclose another factor that might have intervened and affected this migratory fluctuation.

2.1. Hypothesis and Research Questions

The writer's hypothesis is that Greece's newly elected far-left Government, trapped in a situation of economic suffocation deployed a certain rhetoric representing an unjust fight in order to press EU for debt restructuring. As a political strategy, it deployed a rhetoric (and subsequent policies) that could be perceived as invitation to migrants, in order to create a flow as additional leverage, so as to convince Europe for the importance of a powerful and sovereign Greece in the external borders of Europe. Namely, that Greece initiated the strategy of "Coercive Engineered Migration" possibly resulting in the exacerbation of migration to Europe.

In order to confirm the hypothesis the following question must be answered:

- Is it the case the public representation of Greece ,during the negotiations that took place in the first half of 2015 between Greece and EU, to form a rhetoric pattern unsuited to economic fora, which could assign to Greece the position of opportunist coercer?

2.2. Delimitations

This study accepts as a fact that the vast majority of this human flow comprised of asylum seekers and potential refugees without examining the veracity of their assertions as the bare claims would suffice to produce to host countries the afflictions, complexities and implications, the reception of this kind of forced migrants always entails.

The role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) is also considered as decisive and the use of it as a given fact for all migrants on the state of relocation. So, the transition of 'Greek rhetorics' to everyone that could be interested is considered a fact.

The study focuses on the macro level (states) although theories that explain and assess the diplomacy and negotiation tactics and belong to the field of political studies will not be part of the analytic purposes of this study.

As for the CEM implementation, the success or not in terms of whether Greece fulfilled its demands also falls outside the scope. The aim is whether Greece exerted or even attempted to exert CEM in a way that could instigate inflation in the migratory flow.

2.3. Thesis Structure

The structure of the thesis will take the following form:

First, I will map the field in Europe regarding migration. I will briefly present the security status in EU. Then, I will present data that prove an unorthodox shift that occurred in 2015 in the migratory paths towards Europe. With that in mind, I will outline the role of Turkey and then the role of Greece. More specifically, I will expose the political-economic reality of Greece in 2015. The extended historical background is essential for the analytical purposes of my methodology.

I consider essential to deploy a thorough theoretical layout. Refugees, States and institutions/organizations act based on constructed identities. The specific gravity a refugee has compared to an economic migrant cannot be realized unless the refugee establishment and the way it affects States is elaborated. This way, the pressure that was put on EU will be intelligible. Lastly, the Coercive Engineered Migration practice will be presented. Therefore, the theoretical part will be extensive.

Methodology is built upon texts (written and oral) which convey the discursive norms that distinguished members of the Greek administration used. The texts will be elaborated using Critical Discourse Analysis, specifically using the method of Discourse Historical Analysis, a form of CDA, which analyzes data following a three-step elaboration and focuses on identity making, the power relations and the linguistic traits of the discourse.

After analyzing the data my thesis will be culminated with the discussion of my findings and the final conclusions and remarks.

3. Mapping the field in Europe

Migration flows to Europe although are an old phenomenon they never stop ambushing European states due to their constant transmutation in directions and synthesis.

Although the pattern in cases of conflicts had been for the refugees to find shelter to neighboring countries (Zolberg et al.,1989;228) the latest decades “more than ever before refugees are travelling longer distances” (Koser, 2007;75). The establishment of the refugee regime attributed to the western, liberal states the character of the protector of human rights. This along with Globalization that shrunk the world due to “*cheap transportation, nearly instant communications (ICTs) common culture*” (Zolberg et al., 1989;230) are considered the main causes for the up rise of refugees’ arrivals to Europe.

Up until ‘80s Europe seemed to control the migratory flows (Koser, 2007;85) but from 1990 and on when the unrest in Eastern Europe, North Africa and Middle East started (Migration Data Portal, 2018, World Migration Report,2018-chapter 3, p.25) the situation went out of hand and Europe began to show signs of fatigue.

Regardless the European humanitarian tradition, Europe consists of strong nation States, with relatively homogenous populations and ethnic identities. This feature prevails in formulating the politics over migration and asylum issues. The rise of number of irregular migrants/asylum-seekers overcome the rate in which Europe could absorb foreigners and the tolerance of the local populations hence, prompting a growing wave of worries regarding the risk that the presence of so many migrants entails for the economic (jobs and well-fare system) and cultural (different morals and ways of living, assimilation difficulties) life of European States.

EU soon realized that the creation of asylum seekers flows did not constitute just a product of conflict but an outcome of several factors, as problems of economic development, human rights deficit, governance and deeper social issues (Castles et al,2003;33). Therefore, Europe’s initial aspiration was to help in resolving these issues in their birth place hence, preventing the outburst of conflicts that produce asylum seekers. This led to a policy that promoted the interference in the domestic policies of third (origin) states in combination with financial aid which aimed to enhance their economies in order to avoid crises (ibid;35). The plan was proven

to be overoptimistic as overestimated the implementing power of EU over third states. In many cases, these states considered that EU tried to act unilaterally promoting its own interests.

Consequently, EU's reflexes activated on the ground of governmentality, focusing on the deterrence of asylum seekers to enter EU. So, it deployed strategies of securitization. In a series of actions, in order to regulate the management of the incomers in a common way, to share the burden according the principles of solidarity stipulated in the article 80 of the 'Treaty on the Functioning of European Union'² and to securitize the European borders, it created mechanisms of control and surveillance. Building on the spirit of Geneva Convention European countries created the Dublin System (outside the structure of EU so not to be bonded more than with an international convention) which aimed at controlling the entrance of asylum seekers preventing 'asylum shopping' (migrants choosing where to apply) and 'refugees in orbit' (multiple applications) phenomena. In 1999 EU established the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) and created structures as the European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (EURODAC) and the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX).

The fortification of Europe was combined with more strict interpretation of the Geneva notion of refugee, restrictive measures (as detention, limited well-fare provisions) for the asylum-seekers and lastly and most importantly the remote-control policies which involve agreements with neighboring states, as Turkey, in order to handle the asylum-seekers management before they reach European soil (external border management, Gokalp Aras, 2019;191).

Despite all this, Europe faced the migration crisis of 2015 when over a million immigrants entered EU in less than a year.

² Treaty on the functioning of European union art. 80 : The policies of the Union set out in this Chapter and their implementation shall be governed by the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility, including its financial implications, between the Member States. Whenever necessary, the Union acts adopted pursuant to this Chapter shall contain appropriate measures to give effect to this principle.

3.1. The changes of flows from 2014 to 2015

When the Syrian war begun in 2011 Europe already counted many years of accepting refugees from war-blown countries in Africa, Asia, even south America. The Syrian war, the latest episode of Arab spring, although characterized as civil, constituted a more perplexed case. Many foreign powers were involved (USA, Russia, UK, France) along with ISIS which still was a threat to European safety. This particularity along with the geographical proximity rendered Europe sensitive regarding Syrian refugees. Namely, they were not to be ignored.

Refugees initially followed the old patterns of people fleeing war, so, Syrians sought shelter to the neighboring countries Lebanon, Jordan, Iraq and Turkey (host of the lion share).

The intensity of the flows towards Turkey was not aligned with the intensity of the violence and the death toll in Syria.

In years 2012-2013 violence hit the upper limit (Rodgers et al., 2016, BBC) followed by a decline before a second resurgent in 2018. Nevertheless, the flows towards Turkey inflated gradually (figure 1) ending up with Turkey hosting two thirds of Syrians fleeing the country.

This discrepancy rises questions regarding the connection between violence and migrants' decision to choose the northern path towards Turkey and eventually towards Europe.

Although migration scholars as Castles predicted that the increasing worries of European countries for an impeding migration crisis were excessive (Castles et al.,2014;15) the development of 2015 justified these worries as it was the year of an unprecedented influx of migrants to Europe using as main gate of entrance the Turkish-Greek borders.

UNHCR: Syrian Refugees in Turkey

Figure 1

In fact, in 2015 the total arrivals of migrants in Europe reached the number of 1,046,599 (IOM) in a sharp contrast with the previous year (figure 2)(IOM, 2015). 857,363 of them arrived through the Turkish-Greek borders. 56,1% of them were from Syria (50,2% of the total number), 24% from Afghanistan (20,2 of the total number) and 10,3 from Iraq (7,1 of the total number). Apart Syria, both Afghanistan and Iraq are considered asylum seekers' producing countries.

IOM report 2015

Figure 2

Until 2015 the Greek-Turkish marital borders were not the preferred path for migrants on their journey to Europe. It is striking that in Castles, De Haas and Miller's "Age of Migration" book there is a picture depicting the main migratory paths in middle east area in which the path from Turkey to Greece does not even appear (2014,p.182).

The total arrivals in Europe by sea in 2014 reached 219,000 (UNHCR, 2015) with 170,100 coming through Italy 'four times the number registered in 2013, when the Italian authorities recorded 42,925 arrivals' (IOM, 2015c).

The war in Syria had already reached the pick of violence in 2013 and the result was Syrians to comprise the majority of the people fleeing to Italy in 2014 (42,323 Syrians out of the total of 170,100). The interesting fact is that during the same period (2014) the arrivals in Greece reached 43.500 (70% Syrians, 18% Afghans and 4% Iraqis) (Redmond, 2015, UNHCR) indicating that despite the proximity of Greece to Syria the greatest flow was still channeling through the traditional path of Libya-Italy. It is evident that a new game changing factor established the Turkish-Greek path to Europe as the most preferable for the migrants, a factor that emerged in the rise of 2015.

Unequivocally, Europe had to deal with a humanitarian crisis induced by war but the reasons for the 2015 flow through Greece, which enfeebled the Libya-Italy path (42,323 Syrians reached Italy in 2014 and only 7,448 in 2015, IOM 2015 report), needed more convincing explanations.

Could the activation of the strategy of Coercive Engineered Migration by Greece be a valid one?

Before we proceed it is vital to address the theoretical premises that explain why “a refugee” has a special weight in the international migration field and how this distinctiveness can put strain on countries converting migrants into potential weapons, hence emerging the practice of Coercive Engineered Migration.

4. Theoretical Structure

The entanglement of migration issues with politics and international relations creates an interdisciplinary paradigm. The basic theory in which this study is built upon is CEM. The reason why migrants may be transformed into a weapon lies in the special characteristics asylum seekers and refugees possess, compared to other migrants. Therefore I believe it is essential initially to analyze this distinctiveness, to continue by laying out the norms and forces that shape States’ policies, weak points and reactions and, finally, to expound the basic theory (CEM) that connects and gives meaning to all of the above.

Interestingly, the cartoon in thesis’ cover condense the essence of the theoretical development.

4.1. The distinctiveness of Asylum Seekers and Refugees

Asylum seekers and refugees fall within the distinction of Conflict-Induced Forced Migration (distinction by Samers and Collyer, 2017, 9).

The distinction of types of forced migration serves more purposes than just academic accuracy as conflict induced (in comparison with economic development and natural disasters induced) inflicts way more severe practical effects to receiving states due to the privileged treatment these migrants are entitled to.

These obligations exist for the migrants that fulfill the conditions set out in the United Nations “Convention relating to the status of Refugees” (1951) and the modification of the New York Protocol (1967) that extended these rights practically to all human beings³.

³ According to article iA(2) of the Geneva Convention, as it was modified by article i(2) of the New York Protocol, refugee is any person that :

People that are officially recognized as refugees are in a more privileged state than other migrants as “*they have clear legal status and associated rights*” (Castles et al.,2003;6).

Asylum seekers are “*people who move across international borders in search for protection, but whose claims for refugee status have not yet been decided*” (ibid;7)⁴.

The description of the conditions that give ground to people to be granted with the right to enter, stay and be supported by a third country makes clear that the status of refugee is attributed only to those fleeing from persecution, war and conflict, which is a sub-category of forced migrants. In migration literature, forced migration is almost identical to war and conflict induced migration.

Moreover, the refugee legitimization is provided in the Geneva Convention in a strictly personalized way. The interpretation is that each asylum-seeker case is examined individually in its assertion of refugee status. The State is the examiner of the contention whereas the international community has no coercive authority over the States. The parameter of threat, which a conflict produces against the safety of people, is essential for the attribution of the refugee status.

The Geneva convention strictly excludes from protection people forced to move by poverty-induced causes. The phrasing that is used in the relevant provision of the refugee status is persecution, which refers to violence and the effect of violence, a non-measurable factor that can be used as an absolute indication of migration as last resort. This approach adds to the difficulty in detecting who really is a refugee, so as to attribute the status of refugee to immigrants.

In the next part we shall examine, who has the jurisdiction to examine those requests of asylum seekers, highlighting the role of the nation States in the procedure as well as the scope of administrative power in regulating the phenomenon.

“owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to return to it”.

⁴ In the US context the distinction between refugee and asylum seeker refers to the location of the person that applies for protection. When they apply from outside US they are called refugees and when they apply in US they are called asylees retrieved from: https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/refugees-and-asylees-united-states?gclid=EAIaIQobChMI3qGlu--F6gIVDhoYCh1F_wupEAAAYASAAEgIALPD_BwE

4.2. Asylum Seekers-Refugees and Nation States

Migration without sovereign entities would be mere “*moving around*” (Favell et al, 2007; 19). Similarly, the notion of ‘refugee’ is ontologically related to the notion of ‘nation State’ as the first would not have any meaning in the absence of the latter. According to Craig Calhoun (1993 in Cornell and Hartmann, 2007:36) “*nations are envisioned as intrinsically political communities, as sources of sovereignty*”. These political communities are the enclaves of groups of people that among other things as common ancestry, religion, language and nationality, share also territory. Following the syllogism of Hutchinson and Smith (1994:4-5 in Cornell and Hartmann, 2007, 36) “*at the core of nationalism lie three themes: autonomy, unity and identity*”. Autonomy is a prerequisite that requires an autonomous space, hence a territory. Territory “*is thus an area of bounded space*” (Storey 2001 in Samers & Collyer 2017:40). This occupation is exclusive. The national collectivity possesses an autonomous space which is freely accessible only to its members or to third parties after a pre-authorized permission issued by the state, hence the nation exerts sovereignty to its territory. The nation through its institutionalized instruments defines the conditions under which a person who does not belong to its corpus is eligible for entrance to the territory.

The relations between territory and sovereignty are thoroughly discussed and analyzed in Foucault’s work about bio-power and biopolitics. His seminal work provides the theoretical foundation of the broad multidiscipline literature about the interplay and interconnections of the sovereign-government and the population as a subject-object of politics. Foucault argues that western societies have evolved converting their functional mechanisms from juridico-legal, to disciplinary, to security mechanisms (Foucault, 2007:22) not in a successive way but theorizing security as “*a way of making the old armatures of law and discipline function in addition to the specific mechanisms of security*” (ibid, 25). This apparatus of security is orchestrated by the sovereign power of the State within a territory. The function of these mechanisms “*exceed the issue of sovereignty and complicate the question of control*” (Fassin, 2011:214). They cease to primarily make use of the obedience relation between the ruler’s will and the subjected to this will (Foucault, 2007:93). The goal now is to “*manage the social body*” (Foucault, 2010:186) the sovereign-subject relation evolves to government-population relation (Foucault, 2007:100). This management is precisely defined by Foucault as an establishment

which has as its target population and as means “*apparatuses of security*” (Burchell et al., 1991:102) and for which he coined the term “*Governmentality*”. In short, Governmentality aims in serving autonomy, dignity, wellbeing, protection and empowerment of a certain population which is headed by an authority apparatus and connected to a specific territory. The state functions as a power-utility maximizer.

The methodological nationalism of this approach is evident. In this context individuals are operationalized for the sake of the state as a whole (Foucault, 2007, 65). Whoever disrupts the norms as they are ring-fenced by the judicial-administrative establishment is treated as a social threat. In the same spirit, refugees and asylum seekers are distinguished from the population of the state and could be considered causes of potential instability in multiple levels (economic, health, cultural). Foucault pinpoints that “*the government of population is completely different from the exercise of sovereignty over the fine grain of individual behaviors*” (ibid, 94). Albeit, Foucault refers to individuals already members of the legitimate social corpus, even more is applicable to foreigners, as refugees and asylum seekers, who cross borders and force their way into a foreign State. The special obligations States have towards refugees because of their protected legal status create a conflict “*between a commitment to the principles of humanitarian action on one hand and to the principles and norms that underline the ‘peace, security and stability’ of the international system of states*” (Nyers, 2006:2). Namely, the reception of asylum seekers and refugees in the sovereign territory of a third country carries potential threat for its stability.

Governmentality in the management of migrants is translated into “*the development of an administrative apparatus at the borders and within the territory to control immigration and hunt down the undocumented, to adjudicate the refugee status and guard the detained aliens*” (Fassin:218). These security mechanisms include procedures of naturalization, detention, deportation and asylum seekers’ claims examination. The legislation of these procedures normally is an act of sovereignty without any right of review by actors outside the national spectrum. Apparently, these mechanisms are expressions of governmentality therefore the criteria applied for their creation are state oriented. In this vein, the best interest of native population is prioritized over foreigners so discriminative practices against immigrants, considering access to welfare system and rights to work, move or reside, are considered acceptable.

Nevertheless, this homeostatic ‘normality’ within sovereign reality is disrupted by two factors that emerged after the second half of twentieth century, the ‘Up-scaling’ of migration control and the ‘Gap hypothesis’.

-The ‘Up-scaling’ term (along with ‘down-scaling’ and ‘out-scaling’) is coined by Guiradon and Guiradon and Lavav (2000, in Samers and Collyer, 2017:185) and was referring to “*the shifting of decision making on migration and immigration policy from (European) national states to supra-national institutions such as the European Commission or the Council of the European Union*” (ibid:185). Of course, it can be broadly applied to all cases of equivalent inter-states agreements conducted to regulate migration. ‘Up-scaling’ of migration control is distinguished from ‘down and out scaling’ because the two latter forms are within the operational authority of the nation-state either to control, deter or even forbid them. On the contrary, the ‘Up-scaling’ of migration control creates forms that exceed and even supersede nation-states creating pressures in international level that affect international relations and global politics.

Albeit, we cannot speak of global governance regarding economic migration (Samers & Collyer, 2017, 186) things differentiate when it comes to asylum-seekers and refugees. International agreements constitute the railways on which national asylum legislation is moving. As already raised, the Geneva Convention and the consecutive Protocols, ratified by 145 State parties, “*define the term ‘refugee’ and outline the rights of the displaced, as well as the legal obligations of States to protect them*”.

The main principles of Geneva convention are: 1) The “*host state must accord any refugee the same treatment and rights as its nationals receive in respect of legislation, right to property, education, housing welfare benefits and entry to the professions*” (Whittaker, 2006:3) and 2) the principle of non-refoulement “*that is the right of refugees not to be returned to a country when they risk persecution*” (Samers et al, 2017:188) hence, establishing for asylum seekers the right to move whereas it is highly contested and refused to all other kind of migrants (Moses 2006, Miller 2015).

The refugee regime is a palimpsest of international agreements (the 1969 Organization of African Unity (OAU) Convention, the 1984 Cartagena Declaration and the 2004 European Council Directive). Specializations about refugees and asylum seekers rights are also incorporated to international human rights laws and national legislations (Betts, 2009). Even

though, the national judiciary system adjudicates about the legibility of asylum seekers to be granted with the status of refugee, from first to last level, still the international legislative nexus creates a restrictive frame that occasionally contradicts states' interests and always mitigates its sovereign power.

For the EU Member-States this flexibility in the management of immigrants is even lesser. EU's supra-national structure possesses the authority to legislate with mandatory effects for the Member -States. In this context, a very specific 'modus operandi' is created which aims at the burden sharing of immigration flows. The interdependence of EU States becomes evident as the actions of each state have direct impact to the others, hence, adding to the claim that up-scaling of migration control (along with International Law) deprives States from options to confront a potential threat.

The 'Gap Hypothesis' is a term coined (Cornelius and Tsuda, 1994 in Cornelius, Martin & Hollifield) to express the discrepancy between intentions and practices on one hand of mainly western liberal states aiming at reducing incoming flows using the 'apparatuses of security' and the final outcome which is the increase of migration. The 'Gap Hypothesis' is not one factor but the result of multiple variables. According Samers and Collyer (2017:162) the reasons are several as "*states are complex apparatuses which contain many levels and different 'branches' or 'wings', often in conflict with each other*". Freeman's "*Clients Politics*" (1995) and Massey's "*Social Networks*" (1987,1998) are among the possible explanations. A third attempt to explain this gap is the reinforced rights migrants relish in western liberal societies (Hollifield & Wong in Brettell & Hollifield, 2014:243). The reason this study prioritizes 'Rights' over 'Clients Politics' and 'Networks' is that rights are more firmly connected to the sensitive status of asylum seekers whereas the latter two are primarily connected to economic migration. Migrants are bearers of basic human rights, which liberal societies boast they respect and protect. States' commitment for the provision of shelter, health care and even allowances to refugees and asylum seekers create obligations that bear down on the society. On the other hand, the knowledge that liberal states will deliver upon these obligations create a sense of security to people seeking shelter. Consequently, the flows of people towards these states have accelerated the late decades maintaining the discrepancy between intentions and outcomes. Summing up, asylum seekers and refugees in liberal countries have become an unwanted problem that is believed that threatens the equilibrium every society struggles to create (Nyers,

2006:3, Peters in Freeman & Mirilovic, 2016:94). The governmentality mechanisms that aim at the consolidation of security and wellbeing of the State have to confront an intruder which under normal circumstances would be treated according to States' conjunctural interests. Instead, by commitment to international law and conventions, States owe to shelter this potential threat even at the expense of the people they meant to serve. This situation transforms the flows of migrants, especially those constituted by people fleeing war and conflict, into a potential societal bomb and eventually into a factor that can play an important role in the international political scene.

4.3. Refugees in the spectrum of Global Politics

Nation states, their borders and their conflicts are the factors that produce refugees. When the management of refugees involves the interference of two or more States (depending on the migratory paths) it becomes international matter and it is by origin an issue of International Relations. The theories of international relations despite their attempt "*to theorize why states behave as they do*" (Betts, 2009;18) they fail when it comes to forced migration. Western liberal countries are functioning based on "*the political and legal realities of the Westphalian system which is based on the principles of sovereignty and not interference*" (Brettel & Hollifield, 2014;245). Nevertheless, as analyzed in the previous sections, the particularities of forced migration do not permit the use of the same tools with migration in general. Conflict-induced migration is more state and international system oriented. According Betts (2009) nation states are palimpsests of accumulating and sometimes contradicting characteristics therefore their response to conflict induced migration is volatile. Specifically, states are "amoral, self-interested, power maximizers with very little scope for altruistic or moral behavior"(ibid 2009;22). The only way to engage in international cooperation is when this serves their best interests or it is forced upon them due to compliance to other stronger states that have posed a "self-interested hegemony". In this context asylum seekers and refugees are either a security issue or a tool for foreign policy (Teitelbaum,1984)

At the same time western liberal states take into consideration the "global public goods" and the role of "International Institutions" (Betts,2009;26). Concerning refugees, the establishment

of the international refugee regime (as described earlier) had a twofold effect, it serves states interests (security issues) and covered humanitarian need (Betts, 2009;27).

The public belief is that refugees is the side effect of conflict that needs to be managed. The question is: Whose interests this management will serve? On which criteria the State will decide how to react whenever an issue like that reaches its threshold? The international organizations press for the alleviation of the asylum seekers, domestic politics press in both directions according to groups' beliefs and interests, and states, as power maximizers, use them in a way that will improve their place in the international checkboard.

Although exploitation of refugees by States in the international relation level, is in practice for a very long time the acknowledgment by political studies came a bit late. Teitelbaum (1984;437) refers to various forms of migration flows exploitation. The interest of this study is exploitation of ongoing forced migration flows by states' foreign policy and not cases of foreign policy based on past migrations (as unarmed conquest, mass expulsions, creation of buffer zones)

All cases in which states manipulated refugee flows can be filed as a distinct genre of foreign policy which Kelly Greenhill aptly coined "Coercive Engineered Migration" (2010). The logic, the actors involved and the particularities of this special kind of coercion will be further analyzed in the next section.

4.4. COERCIVE ENGINEERED MIGRATION

4.4.1. Definition

According Greenhill "Coercion-driven migrations, or 'Coercive Engineered Migrations' (hereafter CEM) are those 'cross-border population movements that are deliberately created or manipulated in order to induce political, military and/or economic concessions from a target state or states'" (Freeman and Mirilovic, 2016;199). CEM is a subset of a broader phenomenon which is termed by Greenhill "strategic engineered migration" and involves "creation and exploitation of migration crises as means to political and military ends" (Greenhill, 2010;14).

Following Greenhill's theory, Strategic Engineered Migration (SEM) can be divided in three distinct categories according to the reasons it was initiated for:

- Dispossessive Engineered Migration, which aims at the appropriation of a territory and /or extinction of a group e.g. ethnic cleansing
- Exportive Engineered Migration, which aims to diffuse political opponents or strain foreign governments and
- Militarized Engineered Migration, which requires use of military forces in the pursuit of gaining military advantage.

CEM is a non-military tactic that can be found embedded in the above cases of SEM therefore it can be overlooked as a distinct form of coercion (ibid;14). It aims at the same results as military actions, namely, to strain the opposite party as to concede to certain demands. Nevertheless, the threat here is not real bombs but an impending influx of refugees, used as human demographic bombs (ibid;3) that can destabilize the national system in multiple levels. The challenger-states, performing in the context of neo-realist theory, appear as dominance hungry entities that are deprived of morals as they use refugees as pawns to achieve private interests. On the other hand, target-states, balancing in the crossing point of the three theories, face the presence of refugees as a security threat and at the same time, conceding to an international world order, assert allegiance to the refugee regime hence, they provide succor. The provision of help as analyzed in section two entails burdens and dangers for the domestic populations that put the state in a vulnerable position and therefore susceptible to blackmail.

4.4.2. Actors

The general trend is that this strategy is mainly used by weaker states that fall short in resources compared to the target states. The uncertainty of the outcome renders CEM a last resort strategy. Challengers are divided in three categories: 1) Generators, 2) Agents Provocateurs and 3) Opportunists (ibid;23)

Generators are those creating the refugee flows in order to push target states to comply to certain demands. *Agents Provocateurs* on the other hand, are aiming also in extracting benefits from target states not necessarily creating but rather engaging along to an existing crisis that

produce refugees, exacerbating its momentum. This role is more suitable for non-state actors. Sometimes involves groups that victimize themselves, orchestrating activities that cause the aggressive response of oppressive regimes hence, producing more refugees but at the same time gaining support from the target states, it can also involve NGOs.

Unquestionably, actors that deploy such methods must be characterized by serious deficit of democratic and liberal values. Weaponizing humans is a tactic that meets the absolute outcry of the western, liberal world.

Lastly, *Opportunists* interfere in an indirect way. They find themselves somehow involved in a refugee crisis without having participated in its creation. Their action, or inaction, in the management of the refugee flow can have serious implications for third vulnerable states which hence, easily are rendered targets. So, opportunists' willingness to help is depended on certain demands, financial or political, from the third target states (ibid;31). Opportunists need not to be weak or undemocratic. We can find democratic states embracing this implicit role, as the exploitation of the situation can be kept in secret and the outcry can be avoided.

4.4.3. Mechanisms

As nonmilitary strategy CEM needs to activate powers that have the capacity to influence the decision making of state leaders. The threatened influx of refugees is the tool to activate those powers and it is used to disrupt the relation and confidence between the leaders and their supporters/people.

It is no surprise, why CEM is more effective against liberal, democratic States which draw their authority upon grassroot acceptance. In this more or less persuasion game “challengers aim to create domestic conflict or public dissatisfaction within a target state in an attempt to convince its leadership to concede to the demands” (ibid;38) rather than inflict the threat upon the target. Furthermore, the threat is addressed towards states whereas the victims are a third party, the refugees, in a two-level game which is described as ‘coercion by punishment’. This punishment can follow two non-mutually exclusive pathways: 1) “capacity swamping”, namely, challenge of the target society’s ability to accept/accommodate/assimilate the putative refugee influx and 2) “political agitation”, namely, the manipulation of the “willingness of targets to do so” (ibid;38).

Whereas the ‘capacity swamping’ comprises the real danger for both developing and developed countries, especially when the crisis is large and sudden (Greenhill in Freeman and Mirilovic, 2016;209), it is impressive that ‘political agitation’ bears greater fruit as a method of coercion against developed countries which are the main receivers of this type of coercion.

Based on the assumption that a refugee influx constitutes a societal bomb for the receiving societies, one would argue that ‘political agitation’ makes no sense as a tactic as the target state acknowledges the threat and reacts accordingly on its best interest. The reality is more complex than this as the state is not a homogenous entity but rather it comprises of “parties, social classes, interest groups (both economic and noneconomic), legislators and even public opinion and elections, not executive officials and institutional arrangements” (Putnam,1988;432). This ‘Heterogeneity’ (ibid;444) results in controversial reactions to refugees within the same society. Consequently, the division of societies into pro-refugee and anti-refugee camps comes as a common experience to all target states. The demands of each group vary but on the bottom line the pro-refugee camp aims to the promotion of refugees’ interests, demanding from financial support to provision of full benefits of the refugee status, whereas the anti-refugee camp prioritizes the national interest, hence presses for limited engagement to the problem if not total refusal to refugees’ entrance.

The diversity of responses towards refugees is not unexplainable. There is a long history of diverse, good and bad, responding to migrants even by states that are by definition “states of migrants” as US or Australia. We find groups that object to economic migrants in societies that requested their advent as economic labor e.g. Germany, so, how can we not expect even more objection and hostility towards migrants that come uninvited and unwanted as refugees?

Challengers exploit both, society’s fear of becoming overwhelmed, used and enfeebled by the refugees and the ‘heterogeneity’-induced societal upheaval, to exert pressure over leaderships which appear unable to satisfy one party without discontent another and certainly unwilling to bear the political cost of inserting to the system thousands of people that need to be supported, at least at an early face, by the state at the expenses of the citizens. The same citizens that in their majority believe that refugees, and migrants in general, constitute a societal threat (Swain, 2019;16).

Leaders are expected to concede to challengers demands, which usually are of a lesser cost, in order to avoid “general unrest, power-base erosion and make a crisis disappear”

(Greenhill,2010;50). Indisputably, this strategy to have successful outcome it is essential the coercer to persuade the target for the real and upcoming danger and for his absolute power to stop or regulate it (ibid;41).

Lastly, a factor that is not per se a mechanism but rather a “force multiplier” of the momentum of other mechanisms coercers deploy, is the ‘Hypocrisy Costs’. A term coined also by Greenhill (ibid;52) which refers to the vulnerability of a state due to earlier statements of allegiance to the protection of International Human Rights in general or/and due to certain cases in which the target leader, or his predecessors, did assist or made commitments of assisting in previous times. These precedent events create expectations from the state, or the leader, that was engaged in this policy of high liberal values. As a result, every new case of CEM expects/demands from this state to act accordingly otherwise it will be guilty of discrepancy between words and actions. This engagement comes as a result of the altruistic rhetoric leaders use either to attract voters or to promote state agendas in the international level.

4.4.4. Vulnerability of Liberal States

In the absence of global governance states should be sovereign enough to decide their own affairs not being vulnerable to blackmail. In the same vein, the notion of vulnerability seems logical, through the neo-realist lens, only for the weaker states. Nevertheless, reality appears surprisingly reverse.

In Greenhill’s list of CEM cases (1951-now) (Freeman & Mirilovic, 2016;205) USA appears 24 times as target, UN and NATO 18 times, UK and other single cases of European countries 11 times, Australia and Israel 4 times, giving roughly 57 cases out of 80 in total. Should we ascribe the title of western, liberal powers to those countries and alliances then we have to acknowledge that the main target of CEM strategy is the stronger and liberal democracies. The prevalence of the CEM use, almost one yearly, denotes its effectivity and confirms the vulnerability of the liberal states which appear not to choose the use of economic/military superiority to overcome the blackmail but rather concede to negotiations with weaker parties. The neo-realist theoretical approach ebbs and constructivism comes to fill the gaps. States, after all, do interact, argue, counter-argue, change opinions and form politics out of the narrow scope of the strict national interest. The international prestige matters to them hence, admitting

a relation of interdependence with their counterparts. The question why liberal states are more vulnerable finds answer to the inherent features of liberal and democratic values. First, is the allegiance to the human rights regime as this is codified from 1951 and on and it is ratified in the national legislations of liberal states. This commitment entails humanitarian obligations for which the international setting holds liberal democracies accountable. Second, is the “political liberalism” which refers to the “transparent and conflictual nature of political decision making within these states” (Greenhill,2010;60).

Under this prism the vulnerability of EU as consisted of member states with strong democratic values is evident.

5. Turkey, Greece, refugees and CEM

5.1. TURKEY enters the frame of 2015 inflation as it was accused for instrumentalizing refugees hence contributing to the inflation. My intention is to show that there is an explanatory gap.

Cooperation with Turkey was essential in the field of externalization of migration management which become the spearhead of European migration policy. In this context, since 1990 Turkey and Europe deployed a series of actions with upper aim Turkey “to support EU’s external border control through integrated border management, harmonization in the field of visa policy and effective implementation of readmission agreements and the lifting of geographical limitations to the 1951 Geneva Convention” (Gokalp Aras, 2019;190). In return, Turkey was expecting economic support, exemption of Turks from issuing visas to Europe and finally, EU membership. These demands are not fully met until now. Turkey in part tired from the protracted await and partly because of the new role it wishes to embrace, namely, a hegemonic status in the Muslim Brotherhood that visualizes rule of the Arab world, an ambition sparked by the Arabic spring (Roussinos, 2020), initiated a series of provocative actions as part of a broader foreign policy plan.

The sudden migrant influx of 2015, as it was unfolded in the Turkish-Greek borders, rose questions as to what extent it was orchestrated. Turkey was overtly accused that facilitated the passage to Greece-Europe, not complying to its obligations towards Europe regarding the

control and management of refugees in its territory. Migration and political science scholars (Greenhill 2016a, 2016b, Tsourapas 2017, Gokalp Aras 2019) identified in these actions the activation of the CEM strategy on behalf of Turkey.

According Gokalp Aras *“Turkey started to act as opportunist coercer by using this population movement against the EU from mid-2015”* (Gokalp Aras and Mencutek in Gokalp Aras, 2019;191). In the first half of 2015 though, there were clear indications for an upward proclivity of migrants’ arrivals in Europe (figure 2). Aggelos Syrigos, Professor of International Relations in Panteion University of Athens, in his article in Kathimerini (26/4/2015) stresses the disproportionate rise of illegal entries in Greece (70% in January, 160% in February, 476% in March compared to 2014), still no one could conceptualize the huge divergence that would follow until the end of 2015 compared to 2014. Consequently, the term “European Refugee Crisis” appeared in the second half of 2015 (Gokalp Aras,191).

As historic facts do not erupt out of the blue nor political developments happen in a vacuum, it would be a scientific omission not to look for the factors that led to the sudden influx as it started the first half of 2015, when Turkey still had not fully developed its coercive role, and before the shift of the preferable migratory path from that of Libya-Italy to Turkey-Greece.

The thorough examination of the economic and political Greek reality could help in finding additional explanations for the refugee crisis of 2015 and cover the aforementioned explanatory gap.

The next section is devoted to the analysis of this issue.

5.2. GREECE has never openly claimed or admitted the use of CEM nor there is literature about Greece exerting CEM.

A working paper of the Institute of European Democrats (IED) (Nestoras, 2016) is trying to establish a linkage between the change of government in Greece and the migratory inflation of 2015 not attributing the accusation of active facilitation of migrants. The paper focuses on the rhetoric as a populist policy.

The use of CEM tactic is a disgrace for a western, liberal state so there is no chance of admission. It is also difficult to address such an accusation to a western country with strong liberal background as Greece is. In addition, the fact that the coercion took place on an already

existing refugee flow (Greenhill,2010;18), for which another state (Turkey) was already accused for, renders the identification of Greece as CEM opportunist extremely difficult.

What was a certain fact though, was the terrible economic predicament Greece was in.

In the aftermath of the severe economic euro-crisis Greece, a Euro-zone member state, found itself in deep debt crisis with a deficit of 15,4% of the GDP when EU's limit was set in 3% (Greek Statistic Authority, 15-11-2010). The disclosure of Greece's economic situation found both Greek society and EU unprepared. Greek society stubbornly refused to accept the necessity of austerity measures and EU administration refused assisting as European treaties have no prediction for financial aid (Dendrinou & Varvitsioti, 2019, p17) although European banks were dramatically exposed to Greek loans. Out of 252 billion euros in loans to Greek banks 148 were coming from French and German banks (Dijsselbloem, 2018, p47). The existence of the very Eurozone was in jeopardy as the no-rescue rule was in place by the Maastricht Convention (art.125) when at the same time no prediction for member state exit from the currency zone was an option. Concurrently, no common support mechanism had yet activated by the EU (EU established the European Banking Union in 2013 as a response to the euro-zone crisis). Cassandra like voices started to foresee the delusion of monetary union

In May of 2010 Chancellor Merkel made the historic comment "*If the Euro fails, Europe fails*" (BBC, 7-11-2011) and in 2012 Mario Draghi, the President of the European Central Bank, in the same spirit commented "*whatever it takes*" to save Euro (1st youtube video). These comments revealed the uncertainty of Europe concerning a post-Euro era and clearly explain the decision of Euro-members, although unwillingly, to rescue Greece (a scenario initially rejected) hence avoiding the risk of possible Euro collapse.

The rescue had to be executed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF-the only institution that possessed economic power to this extent as to save countries and the expertise for reconstructing destroyed economies) the EU and the European Central Bank (ESB). The three institutions were given the name "The Troika", a term which coined for this partnership with bad connotation to the Greek people. Nevertheless, the submission to an IMF program is internationally considered as humiliation, even worse, when it comes to a western liberal country. Plus, the financial aid is inextricably connected to strict measures, as tax increases, salary-cuts and reforms, that were opposed to deep-rooted habits and vested interests of certain

segments of Greek society. Greece was the first Euro-zone member that needed bailout by IMF. This originality caused embarrassment to all parties involved. IMF had to ebb in requirements that indiscriminately imposed to all other cases of bailout, as debt sustainability, (Hakura, 2020, IMF) and EU granted gigantic loans to a country relatively richer (salaries-wise) than many of other members that had to financially assist.

It is evident that the political cost of this choice was impossible for a government to bear. Between 2009-2015 five governments succeeded one another. The governments that would cooperate with IMF and EU, implementing the reforms in exchange to financial aid, were condemned with political extortion. Therefore, the last two governments came to power using anti-austerity and hostile, against the creditors, rhetoric.

In particular, the first bailout government, elected in 2009 with the 43,92% of the votes collapsed in 2011 under the pressure of the general unrest in society (it gained only 13,18% in 2012 elections). Its successor was a coalition government under the leadership of a former vice president of European Central Bank. Both governments drew gargantuan loans by the creditors (110 billions in 2009 and another 144 in 2011). The coalition government also achieved the implementation of an unbelievable haircut in country's debt, 54% of which was written off, which was held by the private sector. *"That was the biggest debt-restructuring in history"* (Dendrinou & Varvitsioti, 2019, p.19). In 2012, and with the sense that the train was back on track, elections were called once again. After two successive elections a new coalition government came up. The new Prime Minister was known for his resistance in the IMF support. Soon, he realized that there was no other option than follow the program and support the reforms. The political cost was unavoidable. The government fell in January 2015 defeated by the intense anti-austerity movement that swept the society.

These rallies were organized by a small left party with a great momentum between 2010/2015. The small left party by the name SYRIZA (Coalition of Radicalized Left) reached its percentages from 5% in 2009 elections to 36,34 in 2015 elections exploiting an unpredictable opportunity to climb the stairway to power.

At the end of 2014, Greece was a step away from finishing the exhausting race. The final inspection by the creditors was set. Unfortunately, the elections were called for January 2015 due to institutional typicality (SYRIZA would not concede to the election of President) so any severe effort for financial recovery was abandoned for the sake of pre-election campaign.

In this timely short campaign the tense and the division of the Greek people reached unprecedented levels.

Syriza's narrative was nothing less than direct collision with the EU.

A polemic atmosphere was successfully cultivated and in January 25th 2015, SYRIZA won the Greek elections. The new Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras was a genuine intellectual child of the Marxist left, hence critical to liberal economies and nation states.

6. Methodology

I consider methodology as the “process through which one constructs ‘objects of research’” (Bourdieu & Wacquant, 1992 in Fairclough, 2001:8) This essay embarks on the question: “what caused the disproportionate migratory inflation of 2015” and sails to discover whether Greece as direct involved party had any contribution to this. It is a case study dealing with the policies-politics of Greece. The examined period involves the first half of 2015 when the newly elected government starts negotiations with the creditors and the migratory inflation through Greek-Turkish borders begins.

These negotiations, when analyzed in public fora and open interviews were totally sugarcoated. Any leak of the real atmosphere could cause a stir to international markets and would be a terrible blow to EU's success story in a time that BREXIT was imminent. This is why is so essential to highlight the chronicle of negotiations between Greece, which was in total lack of liquidity and begging for financial haircut by the EU.

The claim that Greek politicians intended on pressing the EU using refugees as leverage can hardly be premised in open statements and clear facts. Political processes are implicit and complicated and institutional action is often secretive. The only insight in the intentions of the agents is by observing and analyzing the political rhetoric of the time. The argument of CEM practice can be only speculated based on a synthesis of the discursive information that flooded the public scene, either deliberately or by accident.

The purpose is to find whether the rhetoric and discursive ways of Greek government converge to a pattern, to a strategy. According Fairclough strategies are discourses (2001, 10) hence I

will go through discourses to extract meanings. Therefore, my data, which must re-synthesize the past, will be gathered and analyzed using Critical Discourse Analysis.

Discourse Analysis is about analyzing the language data as evidence for the social phenomena (Taylor,2013:27). My approach will not follow the Foucauldian way of ‘discourse’ which pays little attention to agent’s intentionality, as it perceives him as subject to socially constructed realities (Locke,2004:29). My approach accounts ‘Discourse’ as a practice, as ways of being and doing as well as signifying (Ibid, 7),

What makes Discourse Analysis Critical is the interest in the social formation of the discourse as well as the social effects it produces (Fairclough, 1995: 23). The entanglement of language with power and ideology, the ideological positioning of subjects and the “assymetries of power between participants” (ibid) are crucial in finding the potential social change.

According Fairclough CDA is the appropriate mean to investigate ‘opaque relationships of causality... between discursive practices, events and texts and wider social...structures’. (Fairclough, 1995:132). My research is upon subjects (mainly politicians) that act on the macro level representing states and institutional formations. This social identity they bear does not stop them from using language in order to form identities. Their ideological background, their agenda that might be hidden, their public status that corresponds to a certain power balance are present. Their utterance is the mean to present their truth and to fight into a new aligned reality. My goal is to elaborate upon these utterances in order to find whether there is a deliberate attempt to form a discourse that could alter social reality. Cases that focus on the ‘role of language in power relations, inequality and identity building place themselves under the CDA umbrella’ (Aydin-Duzgit, 2014,357).

The elaboration of the utterances needs a toolkit which is provided by the Discourse Historical Analysis (DHA) as a type of CDA (ibid 358). It has been elaborated in a number of studies which focus on racist discrimination, national identities and discourses about ‘Us’ and ‘Them’ (Wodak, 2001,93). Most importantly, what makes DHC ideal for my essay is that as method gives special attention to the notion of history in the analysis of the texts (Aydin-Duzgit,2014:364). The background of the social texts the social, political environment in which they are created, the ideology of the speaking subjects are crucial for the understanding of the discourses. Therefore, my study persists in highlighting the facts in an historical approach.

In the examined case the interaction (negotiations) evolve between a supra-national organization (EU) and a small and weak member state (Greece). The power asymmetry is evident. This asymmetry enhances the notions of ‘Us’ and ‘They’ in a game of give and take. The new identities that are emerging have nothing to do with national identities. The emerging discourse is about “rich” and “poor”, “weak” and “strong” in an international check board. DHA follows the methodological elaboration of three step analysis which will be analysed in section 6.2 (data presentation elaboration)

6.1. Data Selection and Collection

The selection of my research material is guided by the theoretical framework (Fairclough, 2001,9). Theory provided the view of refugees as a burden to EU, facts proved the will of EU to externalize the ‘problem’ and CEM theory gives the guidelines to search whether a weak player (here Greece) might use the unwillingness of Europe to accept more refugees on its own benefit. As aforementioned the missing pieces of the puzzle involve the way the agents acting for Greece perceive their roles. The key is to find whether there is an agenda, a plan, a strategy that aims at pushing EU into submission. Also, whether that plan is backed up by an ideology and by certain rhetorical pattern in which we can find proofs of that ideology. In the absence of straightforward assumptions the research path is to extract meanings by the utterances, the rhetoric and the public discourse of 2015 interactions’ between EU and Greece.

The utterances are depicted in public statements, epistles, governmental orders and negotiations behind closed doors (as recorded in testimonial books). All data that convey utterances are perceived as texts so texts are not confined to written forms only (Fairclough, 1995,3). Visual data are perceived as texts too and they all are subjected to Textual Analysis as a form of CDA (Fairclough, 2001,8).

Hence, I gathered existing information (secondary data) as they have been circulated in printed publication and in the media which in my estimation disclose to a reliable extent the ‘modus operandi’ of the Greek government.

CDA will be conducted upon data coming from two languages (English and Greek). The translation of Greek talks and documents will be conducted by me.

Data are categorized into two sections as follows:

6.1.1. Testimonial Book

. “Adults in the Room- My battle with Europe’s deep establishment” by Yanis Varoufakis, 2017, Vintage Books. Yanis Varoufakis served as Minister of Finance of Greece (2015, from January to July).

The book is the testimony of the delegate of the Greek government in the negotiations that took place between Greece and EU the first half of 2015. The object of the negotiations was the funding of the Greek economy by the EU. The Greek Minister of Finance Yanis Varoufakis published this book soon after his dramatic service as the main negotiator of Greece during the first half of 2015.

6.1.2. Texts

Secondly, textual data that concern statements of the Greek Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras (1st half 2015) Greek administration. Specifically:

-Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras:

(a) a letter to Herman van Rompuy (Appendix 2) President of the European Commission. The letter was sent one year before his election (b) a statement in the media

(a) The text was extracted from the digital news paper left.gr (27-1-2014)

(b) You-Tube video nr 3 in the references

6.2. Data Presentation – Elaboration

Data presentation will follow the order of the research questions.

First, In chapter 7 the book will be presented and analyzed

Secondly, In chapter 8, textual data that concern rhetoric deployed by the Greek Prime Minister will be presented and analyzed

The material will be analyzed following the three-step method of DHA (Wodak, 2015:93, Aydin-Djurgit, 2014:358).

The method focuses on three dimensions of discourse:

- The discourse topics, namely I will try to investigate whether there is a central theme to a narrative construction
- The discursive strategy, namely the planning, building and iteration of the narrative
- The Linguistic means and features, (Wodak, 2015,93)

The analysis will take the following form:

- Selection of the distinct passages that condense the utterance.
- A short commendation which will provide a first glance and the first impression words bring about to the reader.
- After the presentation of each text an analysis will take place following the DHA three steps method.
- Finally the texts will be cross examined in order to find common elements and/or patterns.

7. Data Analysis

In January 25 2015, SYRIZA won the Greek elections. The new Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras was a genuine intellectual child of the Marxist left, hence critical to liberal economies and nation states. He persistently invested on the narrative that Europe is afraid of the uncertainty of a Grexit and therefore it would easily give in to a debt restructuring, namely another haircut. Moreover, that he would “*abolish the bailout with a single law*” (Dendrinou et al, 27) the moment he would got the power regaining the lost sovereignty.

The new Government heralded the start of the “proud negotiation” the moment it got the power pursuing the ending of the old agreements. The spearhead of the negotiating team was the finance minister of Greece Yanis Varoufakis, a politician elected with solid cause “to say ‘No’ to creditors” (1nd You-tube Video).

The exceptional polemic atmosphere is vividly depicted in the book he wrote about the events of 2015 and his testimony is confirmed and fully aligned with the testimonies of Jeroen Dijsselbloem, president of Eurogroup and spearhead of EU negotiation team in his book about the same events, as well as the book of a third party, the journalists Victoria Dendrinou and Eleni Varvitsioti that thoroughly also narrated the “negotiations” through the lens of journalism.

In the next section I will cite passages from the Varoufaki’s book that will be elaborated linguistically. The notions behind the letters are of our interest.

The original passages are written in italics. I have put in bold words that are further analyzed and to my estimation bear the meanings. The passages are followed by a short linguistic commendation and then the three step DH analysis.

7.1. Varoufakis’ Book

The selected passages from Varoufaki’s testimonial book are the following:

i- *The title “My **battle** with Europe’s deep establishment”*

It starkly states from the very beginning the way the leader of the Greek negotiation team perceives his role as a fighter. He clarifies that there is a fight, a battle where opposite sites take part. The first declaration of ‘Us’ against ‘They’

ii- *Troika was in Athens to “**reduce** Greece’s national income and **place** most of the **burden** of the debt upon the **weakest Greeks**”(p18).*

An obvious statement that EU was considered an enemy. ‘Us’ and ‘They’ again

iii- *“If **they** want (the EU) to **retaliate** by pushing **us** out of the Euro, at immense cost to both **them** selves and **us**, then let them do their worst” (p59).*

Obvious positioning. The pronouns explicitly declare the confrontation. Clear statement for collision plans. The innuendo about ‘cost’ could include the contingency of migrants’ influx as Greece is the threshold into European soil.

iv- *He describes himself and his party as “true internationalists” (p67)*

‘True internationalists’ whatever that means for the free movement of people around the globe and the subsequent obligations of the western countries. The unambiguous translation is that ‘we’ are a different kind of politicians with different aspirations, a new order of things.

v- *“lonely campaign against the most highly weaponized and best prepared creditors in the history of capitalism” (p156).*

Again a statement that better fits to a war than procedures of cooperation . The word against refers to confrontation, so the notion of ‘us’ against ‘they’ persists.

vi- *“attacks ... on the very sovereignty of the Greek state” (p163),*

When a country’s ‘sovereignty’ is at stake some form of war ensues. The word ‘attack’ needs little explanation. The narrative is clearly about conflicting interests, is about making enemies.

Vii- *“War Cabinet”, was the name Varoufakis, the Greek Prime Minister and the team of negotiations gave to themselves (p164).*

The word ‘war’ almost destroys all bridges of communication.

Viii- *“I was threatened (with Grexit)(p 168) by no less a figure than the President of the Eurogroup, with a closure of the banks. Democratic Europe should not tolerate this” (p181)*

‘Threat’, a powerful word that fits between foes. A new element here is the innuendo about the existence of a Democratic Europe which is clearly a third party absent in this interaction. The meaning is that Europe is not governed by Democratic Institutions

ix- *‘debtors’prison’* (p32), *‘disobey EU’s directives’* (p33), *‘humanitarian crisis’*(p37), *‘constructive disobedience’* (p61)

Are examples of the terminology Varoufakis uses throughout the book and create the image of a dystopic present for Greece.

7.1.1. Discourse Historical Analysis

1. **Topic:** It is evident that the Greek minister of finance is trying to build up a case. Let us not forget that the meetings the negotiations took place were economic meetings of the superior European officials. The issue of concern was the financial aid Greece desperately needed. Nevertheless, Varoufakis in a twist of narratives invents a new theme. The new theme is a ‘Battle’ against the *‘highly weaponized and best prepared creditors in the history of capitalism’*. The war of David (*lonely campaign*) against Goliath. For Varoufakis it is not a matter between co-members that assist each other in the context of an alliance. It is an ideological fight (*“true internationalists”*) against *‘capitalism’*.

2. **Strategy:** The narrative was built systematically during Varoufaki’s service. There is a discursive practice which is considered strategy (Reisigl & Wodac, 2015:93). The iteration of the same concept of the *‘Battle’* between the strong and the weak served his purpose of creating certain identities attributing the role of Evil (*‘weaponized and best prepared creditors’*, *‘Troika ... reduce Greece’s national income and place most of the burden’*, *‘If they want (the EU) to retaliate by pushing us out of the Euro’*, *‘attacks ... on the very sovereignty of the Greek state’*, *‘let them do their worst’*) to ‘Them’ and keeping the role of good and weak (*‘weakest Greeks’*) to ‘Us’. This assignment of bad qualities to subjects is recorded as Strategy of Predication (Aydin-Duzgit, 2014:359).

Is an attempt of victimizing the ‘us’. He insinuates that the Democratic Europe exists but it is absent in the negotiations (*Democratic Europe should not tolerate this*). The positioning is clear: Weak, deprived Greece, a victim of international Capitalism, is on a fight against the Capitalist World Order and is asking for the solidarity of the European democratic powers.

3.Linguistic means: Varoufakis builds upon a symbolism. He uses a figure of speech, a ‘metaphor’, to convey drastically his meaning. He compares the interaction with the EU to a ‘Battle’. This metaphor persists throughout his narrative. ‘War’, ‘threat’, ‘weaponized’ are included in the wording he uses, words that are perfectly aligned to the concept of a battle, of a war. In the same vein the words ‘prison’, ‘disobedience’ ‘humanitarian crisis’ are byproducts of the war concept.

Finally, the pronouns ‘Us’ and ‘They’ contribute to the bipolar. At the same time the Predication Strategy is served by the use of verbs with negative meaning as ‘threaten’, ‘push out’, ‘place burden’, ‘retaliate’, ‘attack’. These are the stigma words because they bear the notion of shame to the subject of the action described in the verb.

7.2. Alexis Tsipras- The Greek Prime Minister

The following data are to my estimation important to give an insight in the ideology of the Greek administration as well as they are helpful in making the formulated narrative intelligible. The passages belong to a text written by the prime minister. This choice is justified as the Prime Minister is the main modulator of the governmental policy. The letter is written prior to his election. Nevertheless, I have chosen to use it because it presents a clear narrative that persisted throughout his service and contains comprehensively his beliefs.

i- A letter of Alexis Tsipras to the president of European Council Herman Van Rompuy (Left.gr, 27-1-2014) in which he called for policy reformation of European migration rules. The letter dates one year before his elections but it adds up to sketching the persona and agenda of Greek Prime Minister.

- *'the target of assisting the countries of North Africa and part of the Middle East in order to improve their economies and decrease unemployment was not achieved. Had it been attained, it would have decreased the number of citizens who emigrate to the European Union in any legal or illegal way'*.

In few words, Europe did not succeed in helping so it is held accountable for migrants' lives

- *'it is not realistic to believe that we will halt the inflow of migrants'*

Presentation as a fact of the future inflation of migratory flows

- *'No Frontex force and no fence could stop a phenomenon which is partly a result of the crisis in the countries of origin. Nor shall we achieve it by adopting in the South ever more repressive policies against immigrants under the pressure of the governments of the North of Europe'*

Iteration of the fact of the inflated flows and presentation as a fact of the incapability of Europe to stop them

- *'adopt a legal procedure and a new legal framework, which would efficiently and justly settle access of immigrants to all EU countries, in a fair and proportional fashion, taking into consideration, as far as possible, their own wishes'*

Innuendo that the management might be illegal as well as introduction of migrants as subjects with strong and legitimate will. Their will must be respected

- *'hypocritical and immoral for the heads of various EU institutional bodies, subsequent to a tragic event, to make pompous statements'*

Lastly, the attribution to Europe the accusation of hypocrisy. In addition, an innuendo about the lack of human rights' sensitive administrators in EU administration

ii) A Tsipras' statement in September of 2015 (the inflation was at an outstanding rise) "*There are no borders at sea*" (5th video)

It was a simplified explanation for not guarding the sea borders.

I will analyze both texts simultaneously as they are in the same spirit.

7.2.1. Discourse Historical Analysis

1.Topic: The topic is clearly the migrants and their way to Europe. Tsipras is trying to elevate 'Migration' as a highly important issue moreover to build the case that Europe is responsible for the making of migratory flows. Migrants are struggling to enter Europe. Their struggle is not assisted rather finds Europe defensive.

2.Strategy: The discursive practice follows the pattern of a quilt game. Europe had a '*target*' which was '*not achieved*'. So, The blame goes to Europe. '*Had it been attained, it would have decreased the number of citizens who emigrate to the European Union*'. The message is: not to put on migrants the penalty that should go to Europe. The quilt game also includes implicit creation of identities. 'Us' Migrants (and pro-migrants), and 'They', '*the governments of the North of Europe*', accountable to a great extent. The notion of 'They' is being accused for hypocrisy, immorality and oppression ('*hypocritical and immoral*', '*repressive policies*') hence deploying a 'predication strategy' (Aydin-Duzgit, 2014:359), namely the linguistic assignment of qualities to subjects.

The second trait of this quilt game is the presentation as inevitable realities of issues that are volatile, unpredictable and unknown. '*No Frontex force and no fence could stop a phenomenon*', '*not achieved*', '*Nor shall we achieve it by adopting in the South ever more repressive policies against immigrants*', '*not realistic to believe that we will halt the inflow*'

There are no borders at sea'. It seems like he pursues to present a reality with fix characteristics that cannot be contested. The narrative suggests : 'there are no border at sea, don't spent time and effort stopping the flows'. If Europe accepts it then available sources will be channeled for a good cause (*'adopt a legal procedure and a new legal framework, which would efficiently and justly settle access of immigrants to all EU countries, in a fair and proportional fashion*). Finally, the elevations of migrants us subjects with legitimate rights that reach the point of deciding for their allocation (*'taking into consideration, as far as possible, their own wishes*').

3.Linguistic means: The writing manner of the letter is realistic and political. No metaphors or perplexed speech forms. We notice strong negative wording '*No Frontex force and no fence could stop a phenomenon*', '*not achieved*', '*Nor shall we achieve it by adopting in the South ever more repressive policies against immigrants*', '*not realistic to believe that we will halt the inflow*', '*no borders*'. The persistent repetition of 'no' conveys a twofold meaning, a certainty about the inability to control the flow and an implicit message that there is (at least by him and his ideological partners) no will to stop the influx.

The repeated 'Nos' describe the wrong 'management' of the flows.

The good management of the flows is described by a different figure of speech, adjectives: '*legal*', '*efficient(ly)*', '*just(ly)*', '*fair*', '*proportional*'. The contradiction is intense as the negativity of 'No' is repulsive whereas gentle adjectives create a wish to fulfill what is '*legal*' '*just*' and '*fair*', meaning a favorable policy of tolerance for the people that wish to come to Europe.

The use of adjectives is appropriate for serving the 'predication strategy' as well. The heads of EU are described as '*hypocritical*' and '*immoral*'. Adjectives enhance the connection of 'they' with the other which is hostile and inhuman.

7.3. Crossing Narratives-Discussion

The two texts although they were created for different occasions and refer to different facts they have astonishingly too many common features.

They both build upon a narrative in which Europe is the culprit. The ‘Predication Strategy’ is deployed in both cases to create the separation of ‘Us’ from ‘They’. ‘They’ in both stories is European Union. European Union is presented as the highly energetic perpetrator of many unpleasant verbs (*threaten*, *push out*, *place burden*, *retaliate*, *attack*) in Varoufakis discourse and an entity with *hypocritical* and *immoral* heads in Tsipras discourse.

They both insinuate that democratic, human rights’ sensitive Europe is absent from the administration. To conclude, ‘They’ in both narratives is EU and it is identified as the bad.

The question is, ‘who is the good’?

In Varoufakis discourse the identification is easy, ‘Us’ is ‘Us Greeks’. The impoverished people asking for more loans detached from obligations. In Tsipras case it is a bit more complicated as ‘Us Greeks’ are part of the EU. But by no means ‘Us Greeks’ belong to ‘They-Bad Europe’. So, Tsipras bisects Europe with a simple phrase *‘repressive policies against immigrants under the pressure of the governments of the North of Europe’*. Europe is instantly divided into two pieces, North and South. South, particularly Greece, as financially supportable state identifies itself to the weak, hence closer to ‘Us-migrants’. Consequently, the conceptualization of ‘Us’ does not differ in the two narratives. As long as Greeks are weak they belong to the defensible ‘Us’.

Lastly, following this reasoning we realize that the topic is also common to both narratives. ‘The battle of Greece’ and the ‘struggle of migrants’. Both victims of a world system, both in a fight for a better life.

The similarities of the narratives lead us to consider that they are complementary to each other. They form a collective narrative with more nuances expressed by different delegates of the same administration.

8. Narratives and CEM

Throughout 2010s Europe accepted numerous people that were given the benefit of being considered refugees, until proven otherwise. This happened in full contradiction with the belief that states act free of morals and treat refugees as security bombs. In fact, European states appeared welcoming in the public scene up until 2015 although the truth was that refugees were

proven to be destabilizing factors for the receiving societies. Yeroen Dijsselbloem, the President of the Eurogroup during the negotiations with Varoufakis in his book “The Euro-Crisis” (2018:170) refers that a migration crisis reached the point of almost overturning his government. So, even though no European official overtly admitted, no one wished for more refugees in European soil.

As for how EU perceived the role of Greece it is interesting to take Barack’s Obama theorization. He devotes several pages of his book “A Promised Land” (2020) in the Greek Matter, describing Greece’s debt crisis as the dynamite in the premises of the European Structure (p556 of the Greek version) confirming also his stand for Greece’s geopolitical importance (p558).

According Greenhill states that activate CEM are usually weak states that are deprived of other ways of dominance as economic influence or military means (2010,1). Greece was certainly deprived from both options. Its feeble position against its creditors is a given fact. At the same time Greece had full acknowledgment of its geopolitical positioning. Therefore, Greece’s new government was about to start ‘proud negotiation’, a ‘battle’ (Varoufakis, 2018:66).

Greenhill (2010,28) accounts that states unwilling to stop or regulate refugee flows at the expenses of third vulnerable states have the potential status of becoming opportunist coercers. What usually generates this attitude are certain demands, financial or political. The knowledge we have is that Greece had desperate need of financial support so the motive of financial demands is there. What is unknown is the explicit admission on behalf of Greece that it would not assist any effort to stop the flows hence, multiplying the phenomenon as news of easy entrance travel fast amongst refugees, especially to those in limbo state in Turkey.

In the absence of affirmative statements from the Greek administration concerning the flow management the only insight we can have in government’s intentions is its public narrative. Then we can estimate whether it is compatible to the facts.

Critical Discourse Analysis showed that the narrative both, Varoufakis’ and Tsipras,’ converged to a great extent and it was aiming at disrupting the confidence between the leaders (of the EU) and their supporters, to create public dissatisfaction. The innuendos by both that the heads of EU are immoral and strange to the democratic people of Europe were a deliberate attempt to destabilize the institutions. This tactic is considered to be a classic CEM tactic as creates ‘political agitation’ to the target states (ibid:38). The infliction of the threat upon the

target or even the articulation of the threat when it can be assumed by the context is not a constituent element for attributing the role of coercer to a state. That means that mere accusations are enough to coerce the target state (or target states that consist EU), even more when it is a union as liberal as Europe. Even more when the “heterogeneity” of the society is adding up to its vulnerability (Putnam, 1988:444) and the public opinion being tired from the constant past migratory flows. In addition, the contingency of exerting CEM by Greece is enhanced by one more factor the activation of ‘Hypocrisy Costs’ (Greenhill, 2010:52) by the Greek Prime Minister. Tsipras in his letter clearly accused Europe for Hypocrisy when it comes to migrants.

Lastly, the accusation for inhuman treatment to migrants addressed to the heads of EU by a person that rules a country-potential gateway to Europe is an immediate danger that can easily be perceived as threat. In parallel, they would be consistent to their ‘Internationalist’ beliefs.

In conclusion, the presupposition of Greece’s leaders against the institutions of EU, their clear intention to press Europe and the wish to facilitate migrants is obvious. Whether this is enough to provoke the influx is impossible to be proven in a positivist way.

In this context, 2015 started bringing the shift of the preferred path to Europe (see 3.1) as Greece is experiencing 476% increase in migrants’ entries until March (less than three months of SYRIZA governing). War is an inadequate justification for this particular inflation. Out of the blue Italy received only 7.448 Syrians in 2015 when the number in 2014 was 42.323 under the same war conditions. The shift of the main migratory route towards Europe is indisputable and also unexplainable by the already existing war and conflicts conditions.

Europe at that time was just overcoming a Euro-crisis and was still struggling for unity so, it was assumed that it would not jeopardize another prolonged crisis. Also, it was known that Europe experienced great puzzlement due to the conflicted roles that it had to serve concerning the accumulating numbers of refugees: a beacon of human rights on one hand and guardian of European stability on the other. In SYRIZA’s political agenda, as of which role should prevail, the choice was already made. Europe, checking all the boxes of western liberal democracies had always been at high vulnerability and hence exposed to CEM practices.

Greece was found involved in a refugee crisis with no responsibility for the generating causes. The initiative by the Greek government to act as refugee defender consisted an implicit and

silent manipulation without risking the identity of a western liberal state that respects human rights (Greenhill,2010, 31)

Greece definitely fit the profile of the ‘opportunist’ coercer the time it appeared in the European scene (January of 2015) quite impoverished and depended (total lack of other recourse) but still demanding and offensive, pressing for ‘battles’.

The range of actions that exemplify CEM is quite hazy. According Greenhill CEM is deployed in a ‘persuasion game’ where sole threats can result the requested concessions (2010,38). On the other hand, the Prime Minister and his inner cycle had to deal with a win-win situation. Their aspiration was to re-negotiate with Europe’s “deep establishment” (Varoufakis,2018) and to create a Europe of solidarity and open borders according to the narrative they deployed. To their great satisfaction the two goals could perfectly combined.

With these remarks in mind we can diagnose that Greece did deployed a polemic against Europe and a pro migrant narrative, a rhetoric pattern which was served diligently. This attitude is perfectly aligned with an implicit exertion of CEM and unquestionably did coincide to a massive, unprecedented influx which up until now has not yet received a convincing explanation.

9. Conclusion

The root cause that led to this essay emerged from the simple question: “Why 170.100 migrants entered Italy in 2014 and 153.842 in 2015, whereas 43.500 entered Greece in 2014 and 857.363 in 2015 (IOM)?” For me as a researcher, the challenge was to ascertain what, other than war, could be the causes.

The theoretical analysis rendered intelligible that Europe as a Union with strong liberal values was trapped between the principles put in place by its institutions concerning the allegiance in human rights regime and the reality of fortification of Europe and the externalization of the refugee issue. The accusations Tsipras made about ‘Hypocrisy’ hit a sensitive cord as having a solid ground. Europe was accused of not helping the weak and Greece was amongst the weak. The narratives was combined in sending the message: Europe owed to help the weak and/or ‘us-weak’ we will help each other. The signal of solidarity was sent by Tsipras administration

not only to the co-members of Democratic Europe but to all impoverished people. Therefore, the flows towards Greece rose by 476% the first months of service of the new government.

As was theoretically presented it is possible for a liberal state to embrace the role of opportunist coercer, even though, it is a disgrace for a state with strong liberal values to exploit the predicament of migrants. The exploitation takes place implicitly. No states-man would ever make an open statement or there was ever the chance of admission. The practice is proven by the results, which being the almost a million migrants coming in Europe through Greece in a 2015

The data analysis confirmed the hypothesis that there was a new game-changing factor, that being the Greek new political scene and its rhetoric. Although no concrete evidence was unearthed that can support an open exertion of CEM by Greece Discourse Historical Analysis of the Greek narratives revealed a presupposition of the Greek administration to open the borders. That strategy was perfectly aligned with the second strategy of pushing Europe (the 'unfair they') into submission in an unconditioned financial aid.

10. Final Remarks

As the main goal is to find and give meaning to acts that took place in Europe and Greece in 2015, the presentation of political circumstances in combination to the beliefs of the politicians that represented the Greek state at that time was of major importance as intentions can lead to meanings of certain actions by interpretation (Rosenberg, 2015, 56). So, the investigation of intentions of actions in order to make the actions intelligible are a massive goal. These actions cannot be confirmed as causes but they can become intelligible to us not by all means reducing the value of the research (Rosenberg, 2015,43).

To carry through with my query, whether the practice of CEM was exerted, I gathered data (videos, newspapers, epistles, statistical data) that present facts, statistics and statements of great value as they cannot be juggled, hence adding validity to my essay.

Naturally, there is a vast amount of information that cannot be incorporated in this thesis and there is always the case that new evidence can overturn old conclusions. Nevertheless, I would contend that even if a future researcher challenge my argument about CEM practice by

presenting new evidence, it could not be disputed that Greek political stand might have enhanced migratory inflation.

More importantly, the material was processed critically. My main concern was to be cautious with inferences in order to be intelligible. Therefore, I tried to connect beliefs, facts and results in order to draw conclusions. Therefore, I contend that the argumentative build-up of the case was firmly completed.

Finally, the topic could not be exhausted. There is an open question mark whether Greece succeeded in its aspirations. There are solid arguments for opposite answers. But this may be the ground for another treatise.

APPENDIX 1

Athens, 25 January 2014

Mr Herman van Rompuy

President of the European Council

Mr President of the European Council,

The loss of life of hundreds of immigrants in the seas of South Europe continues undiminished. Subsequent to the drama of Lampedusa, nine children and three mothers tragically lost their lives, only a few days ago in the North Aegean Sea.

To this day, the initiatives undertaken by the European Union (EU) to tackle immigration in the countries of origin had no measurable results. The programmes designed to support the Barcelona Declaration were effectively abandoned, without having achieved any of their targets. For certain, the target of assisting the countries of North Africa and part of the Middle East in order to improve their economies and decrease unemployment was not achieved. Had it been attained, it would have decreased the number of citizens who emigrate to the European Union in any legal or illegal way.

In addition, wars in the wider Mediterranean region and the Middle East, which are a further basic cause of migration flows, have intensified, increasing those flows and multiplying human tragedy in the Mediterranean Sea.

Let me remind you that, from 1998 to 2013, at least 17.000 human beings lost their lives during their effort to emigrate to the EU. The United Nations estimates the current level of migrants on a world scale to 214 million. That is, close to 3% of world population. Therefore, it is not realistic to believe that we will halt the inflow of migrants, that is, of people who are seeking a better life in the EU countries, by constructing ever taller walls.

No Frontex force and no fence could stop a phenomenon which is partly a result of the crisis in the countries of origin. Nor shall we achieve it by adopting in the South ever more repressive policies against immigrants under the pressure of the governments of the North of Europe.

In that context, it is necessary to immediately review the overall EU institutional framework for immigration and asylum, in the direction of ensuring the protection of fundamental human rights on the entire European soil.

It is absolutely necessary to immediately plan efficient measures to rescue migrants on the open sea, to set up reception centers at the entry points, and adopt a legal procedure and a new legal framework, which would efficiently and justly settle access of immigrants to all EU countries, in a fair and proportional fashion, taking into consideration, as far as possible, their own wishes.

It is hypocritical and immoral for the heads of various EU institutional bodies, subsequent to a tragic event, to make pompous statements, which are forgotten once TV cameras leave the sites of tragedy that they have visited.

Ambitious proclamations, when not supported by concrete actions and transformed into adequately funded policies, act as a brake on the efforts of the EU South countries to tackle that huge humanitarian problem.

I believe that Europe has the historical duty to immediately shape an overall immigration policy, which would ensure human rights and serve European values.

Mr President of the European Council,

Following the repeated and recent tragic events in Lampedusa and Farmakonisi, I ask you to immediately take the initiative, according to article 15, para. 3 of the Treaty on European Union and convene a special meeting of the European Council as soon as possible, with the subject of having Council Regulation (EC) No 343/2003 (Dublin II) revised, according to article 80 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union that EU policies on immigration shall be governed “by the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility, including its financial implications, between the Member States”.

I also request that your initiative comprises the urgent release of funds to effectively tackle that humanitarian problem, which continually worsens, in the context of the relevant provisions for emergency situations.

Sincerely,

Alexis Tsipras

President of SYRIZA

Candidate of the Party of the European Left

for the Presidency of the European Commission

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